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Inclusivity Framework for Energy Communities

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1. About the Inclusivity Framework

Inclusivity in energy communities can be understood as ensuring that energy transitions in local communities are affordable, accessible, secure, reliable, and fair for everyone, especially those who are vulnerable or experiencing energy poverty, based on an equal distribution of benefits and burdens¹. Although energy communities have the potential to democratise energy access and empower citizens, there remains a significant gap in both practice and policies concerning effective inclusivity integration. Without deliberate efforts to implement inclusive measures, energy systems and processes risk being dominated by certain socio-demographic groups or elites, thereby excluding marginalised groups, particularly those experiencing energy poverty, and limiting their influence and participation in decision-making.

This document sets out an Inclusivity Framework for Energy Communities. Outlining six different modes of inclusivity, this Framework looks to identify the various barriers and challenges to participation, particularly among vulnerable groups, and proposes practical and actionable recommendations for municipalities and other organisations involved in the energy transition to enhance inclusivity.

Whilst it is tempting to interpret such a frame hierarchically, with each subsequent mode of inclusivity improving on the previous, it is important to bear in mind that certain modes of inclusivity complement different goals, scales, and contexts. In any given community, elements from various modes of inclusivity may exist simultaneously or even overlap depending on how they are put into practice.

Tips for using the Framework

There are multiple ways to use this Framework - from reflecting on and assessing the structures and practices of your own organisations to envisioning ways to seek out and bolster your efforts to foster inclusivity. Amongst other uses, this Framework may be used to:

- Better understand the areas in which inclusivity can be enhanced.
- Help identify some of the practices your organisation undertakes.
- Assess future steps and strategies for fostering the type of inclusivity relevant to your goals, mandate, or community.
- Reflect on the people or communities your organisation seeks to serve.
- Focus on the organisations, schemes, and groups you might work with to achieve change.

¹ Weijnen, M.P.C., Lukszo, Z., Farahani, S. (Eds.), 2021. Shaping an Inclusive Energy Transition. Springer International Publishing, Cham. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-74586-8>

2. The inclusivity Framework

The Inclusivity Framework outlined below provides different modes of inclusivity in energy communities, and examples of concrete actions that municipalities can take during the setup and operation of energy communities to enhance inclusivity.

The Inclusivity Framework for Energy Communities provides a nuanced spectrum to understand and enhance inclusivity within energy communities. We pay particular attention to irradicating any experiences of exclusion, such as those faced by vulnerable or marginalised groups facing energy poverty. The Framework has been developed by drawing inspiration from the ladder of participation Framework² and the spectrum of public participation model³, and is grounded in broader understandings of inclusivity from Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) literature. This Framework outlines six different modes of inclusive citizen engagement and participation, as shown in the Figure. As we transition from passive towards more active and transformational modes, inclusivity becomes more comprehensive. This shift moves from discrete inputs through singular and narrow processes to advocacy and alliance-building aimed at achieving systemic change.

2 Arnstein, S.R., 1969. A Ladder of citizen participation. J. Am. Inst. Plann. 35, 216-224. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01944366908977225>

3 The International Association for Public Participation's spectrum of public participation model. <https://organizingengagement.org/models/spectrum-of-public-participation/>

3. The six modes of inclusivity

1. **Passive inclusivity:** whilst highlighting the importance of diverse citizen involvement, this mode of inclusivity highlights a passive approach⁴ without active engagement or policy adjustments.

For energy communities this entails open-door policies that are generic and not specific to a particular group. While there is acceptance for the need for greater diversity in energy communities, it does not translate into any active or targeted engagement.

A municipality may promote the concept of energy communities or promote existing energy communities through campaigns and general policies to generate interest.

2. **Informal inclusivity:** targeted efforts, like information campaigns or subsidies addressing the exclusion of vulnerable groups. Unlike passive strategies, this entails active steps towards inclusion often manifesting in one-off participatory events.

For energy communities, this approach may entail an informal level of inclusion, with occasional efforts to include diverse citizen groups, primarily through informal or one-off events as a form of compensation for their inclusive participation. This could include hosting informal sessions with community leaders from marginalised groups to discuss energy needs and barriers.

A municipality may undertake consultations on needs of pre-determined vulnerable groups or support one-off subsidies or actions in which targeted assistance is offered to help them with the (administrative, financial or other) first steps necessary for joining an energy community.

3. **Compensatory inclusion:** focuses on creating explicit policies (and definitions) that respect diversity and alternative perspectives, and aim to increase community representation, especially from vulnerable and low-income groups. May take the form of subsidies or legislation striving for equality by offering formal support.

For energy communities this mode of inclusivity requires that demographics of EC members reflect the wider regional population. It focuses on addressing disparities across ethnicity, gender, income, and class.

A municipality may develop training or regulations for energy communities that encourage member diversity, provide funds for hubs to help initiate energy communities, or act as an intermediary to connect a prospective community to target groups.

4. **Inclusive participation:** promotes a culture of deliberation and reflexivity⁵, actively addressing exclusions in problem framings, participants, and the process of participation. Greater transparency and accountability are seen as central to ensure equality in decision-making and the active inclusion of diverse and marginalised voices.

For energy communities an inclusive participatory approach involves collaborative decision-making. It ensures that projects are co-created with the active participation of all community members, especially focusing on those affected by energy poverty. It is reflexive of any partialities and exclusions and open to more diverse forms of participation, ensuring a more fair and transparent process.

A municipality may develop regulations or training that encourages energy communities to structure decision-making in collaborative and co-creative ways. A municipality may also offer resources to support initiatives and events where these processes are designed.

4 Grossmann, M., Creamer, E., 2017. Assessing diversity and inclusivity within the Transition movement: an urban case study. *Environ. Polit.* 26, 161–182. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09644016.2016.1232522>

5 Chilvers, J., Pallett, H., Hargreaves, T., 2018. Ecologies of participation in socio-technical change: The case of energy system transitions. *Energy Res. Soc. Sci.* 42, 199–210. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2018.03.020>; Chilvers, J., Stephanides, P., 2023. Mapping Participation for Democratic Innovations: An experiment in evaluating a citizens' panel on h. <https://doi.org/10.5286/UKERC.EDC.000966>

5. **Empowered (vulnerable voices):** empowers diverse groups in ECs through their involvement in leadership roles, significantly influencing community decisions. Empowerment can be understood as giving authority or power to the people, with the ability to choose self-inclusion or self-exclusion without risk. Empowering interventions lead to a sense of impact, motivation, self-determination, the ability to choose, and feelings of self-efficacy⁶.

For energy communities this involves focusing on who is empowered and which citizens in the community are given decision-making roles and influence key project outcomes, emphasising inclusivity in the processes of energy community development.

A municipality may help develop regulations for energy community founders that encourage leadership roles to be taken up by marginalised community members, offering tools to take control over various aspects of societal daily life.

6. **Transformative inclusion:** Transformative inclusion aims for deep changes in socio-technical systems, challenging existing power dynamics⁷ to address broader societal issues. Organisations cannot often do this alone but require forging alliances and coalitions to advocate for wider systems change.

For energy communities this entails reflecting on the organisations, movements, and communities they may need to work alongside to create systems change. This is pertinent for the wider changes energy communities seek to create, especially when current economic and regulatory systems pose barriers to the establishment of inclusive energy communities.

A municipality may help connect and develop an energy community's network of organisations and integrated support systems with whom they might collectively advocate and campaign for common causes and wider systems change.

6 Hanke, F., Lowitzsch, J., 2020. Empowering Vulnerable Consumers to Join Renewable Energy Communities—Towards an Inclusive Design of the Clean Energy Package. *Energies* 13, 1615. <https://doi.org/10.3390/en13071615>; Thomas, K.W., Velthouse, B.A., 1990. Cognitive Elements of Empowerment: An “Interpretive” Model of Intrinsic Task Motivation. *Acad. Manage. Rev.* 15, 666–681. <https://doi.org/10.2307/258687>

7 Grossmann, M., Creamer, E., 2017. Assessing diversity and inclusivity within the Transition movement: an urban case study. *Environ. Polit.* 26, 161–182. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09644016.2016.1232522>

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Adjoining material

[Towards Inclusive Energy Communities in Arnhem Serious Game webpage](#)

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